

IMPACT OF WASTE ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: *The importance and relevance in modern society of the problem of the negative impact of production waste and consumption on objects of the natural environment and the state of health of the population are associated with their daily education, large tonnage, storage, and disposal. Waste and places of their storage and disposal pose a toxicological and epidemiological hazard. Chemical and biological contamination of solid waste poses a threat of its penetration into the soil, atmospheric air, underground and surface water bodies, vegetation and can directly or indirectly cause deviations in the health status of the population.*

Key words: *toxicological, epidemiological danger of production and consumption wastes; impact of waste on the environment and public health*

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Pollution of the biosphere with solid domestic and industrial waste due to the growth of their scale and dynamics, the ability to have a negative impact on human health and the natural environment is a global environmental and hygienic problem of our time.

Given the ubiquity, large tonnage and daily generation of waste, it becomes obvious that this problem is one of the most important and relevant at the present time. In most countries, according to various estimates, 600–1200 million tons of solid waste have been accumulated, about 30 million tons (140 million m³) are formed annually, 95% of the generated solid waste is disposed of.

The placement of waste at landfills in the world is primarily due to the insufficiently high level of economic development, the lack of domestic specialized industries, the economic unprofitability of waste processing, as well as the imperfection of the legislative framework in the field of waste management.

Society is not sufficiently aware of the real and potential danger of solid waste, the need to change the system for handling them. The world can have varying degrees of chemical contamination and pose a toxicological hazard. Waste collected from dwellings and residues resulting from the incineration of household waste are classified as hazardous.

Municipal waste may contain significant amounts of toxic chemicals. According to the literature, the average concentrations of heavy metals (zinc, manganese, copper, chromium, lead, mercury, etc.) in the world have increased by 1.6–3 times over the past 4 decades. In the 80–90s of the last century, it was found that compost prepared from household waste significantly exceeds soils in terms of the content of a number of toxic

elements (1.5–2 times content of lead, zinc, copper, molybdenum, silver and 10 times - mercury).

Currently, more than 100 substances, defined as hazardous, are used in everyday life. First of all, heavy metals are emitted (cadmium and nickel contained in batteries, consumer electronics, plastics, paints; lead - in paint, electrical wiring, car batteries; mercury - in fluorescent lamps, etc.), various types of pesticides, as well as substances contained in cleaning products, varnishes, etc. Up to 40% of the world is used packaging, the polymer part of which reaches 50%. In the traditional disposal of waste at landfills, the polymer fraction decomposes extremely slowly (50–100 years). The combustion of polymers leads to the formation of highly dangerous toxicants - polychlorinated biphenyls, dioxins, benzofurans, etc.

Fly ash from waste incineration plants is enriched with chlorides (a highly soluble form) of heavy metals, including toxic ones such as lead, cadmium, and zinc. Most countries pose a serious epidemiological hazard.

According to the chief state sanitary doctor of the Russian Federation G.G. Onishchenko, as a result of the unsatisfactory organization of the collection and disposal, microbial contamination of the soil is formed. The epidemiological danger of solid waste is mainly associated with their biological contamination (the presence of pathogenic bacteria, protozoa, viruses, helminth eggs in them) and the role of epidemiologically significant synanthropes (rats and flies) in reproduction. The soil around the garbage containers within a radius of 15 m is highly polluted in terms of microbiological indicators. The direct epidemiological danger of household waste can also be traced in terms of sanitary and helminthological indicators. The epidemiological danger is increasing in case of violation of the system of separate collection, disposal and disposal of waste treatment and prophylactic institutions - more than 90% are collected and removed through a single system with solid waste to landfills and landfills.

Cases of infection of people with HIV infection, hepatitis B, vaccinia from medical waste thrown into general waste bins have been registered. Sanitary requirements provide for the exclusion of the possibility of human contact with waste, the maximum mechanization of the processes of their purification during collection, removal, disposal and neutralization. However, in practice, public utilities workers, are contaminated with pathogenic microorganisms (hand skin, overalls) during work, which creates precedents for the emergence and spread of diseases. According to periodic medical examinations, the workers of landfills and salvage shops have a decrease in the body's resistance, which leads to the emergence of various infectious diseases. The first place in terms of the frequency of cases and the number of days of incapacity for work is occupied by tuberculosis, among loaders - influenza and acute respiratory diseases, pustular skin diseases, diseases of the peripheral nervous system. There is evidence of a high risk of morbidity in adults and children (mainly respiratory and gastrointestinal disorders tract) in the residential area in the zone of influence of the landfills.

A serious problem is the pollution of environmental objects with solid waste. Landfills and burial sites are sources of soil pollution, water from underground sources, open

reservoirs, and atmospheric air . The lack of systems for collection, disposal and purification of the leachate leads to pollution of surface and ground waters and can be easily washed away by water currents. In addition to heavy metals (cadmium, mercury, lead etc.), in the aquifers of urban landfills, an increased content of oil products, various organic compounds, high mineralization created by high concentrations of chlorides, sulfates, phosphates, nitrates, sodium, potassium, and ammonium ions in the landfill filtrate were found. With hydraulic connection with surface water bodies, with surface runoff from various areas of waste disposal into water bodies, the ecological balance in them is disturbed, contributing to their eutrophication . In addition, a high content of coliform bacteria in the water of these open reservoirs was established.

The solution to the problem of the negative impact of production and consumption waste on the environment and human health lies in the coordinated, well-coordinated and operational work of many services and organizations related to this issue - local governments, urban planning councils, environmental protection services, bodies and organizations , public utilities, industrial and agricultural enterprises.

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